

PARAGA GAME AS TRADITIONAL SPORTS FOR BUGIS MAKASSAR TRIBAL COMMUNITIES IN SOUTH SULAWESI, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

The current study aims to identify 1) the developmental history of *Paraga* game in South Sulawesi, 2) the way how to play *Paraga* game by the communities, 3) the movement skill aspects, and 4) the physical ability aspects. The research was conducted in center cultural exhibition that foster and preserve the game located in South Sulawesi. The current study used qualitative descriptive method using the research subject of *Paraga* game as the traditional sport of Bugis Makassar Tribal Communities in South Sulawesi. It contains movement skill and physical ability aspects in playing *Sepak Raga* attractions. The data were collected by using several techniques such as observation, documentative recording and interview. The results of *Paraga* game as a traditional sport of Bugis Makassar tribal communities in South Sulawesi Indonesia can be concluded as follows: 1) The history of *Paraga* game of Bugis Makassar tribal communities in South Sulawesi since past until today has shifted its functions, even among communities in South Sulawesi who had already considered it as traditional sports and cultural heritage which should be well preserved. Based on the history of *Lontara*, this game was performed as an entertaining media, event for the inauguration of the king (*somba*) of Gowa kingdom to entertain the royal guests. The first *Bola Raga* was played when the game was being discovered and performed by "To manurung" a sport derived from heaven, and made of gold (*raga bulaeng*). Along with the development of this game in the communities, a village named *Paraga* was found in Dusun Kaemba that is Ujung Bulu that had been visited by a king (*karaeng*) of Gowa kingdom. He spread Islam and introduced traditional musical instruments, especially

drum (*ganrang*) and *gong* which made a *Paraga* appearance was no longer displayed with common movements, but it has been now accompanied by traditional musical instruments. It was certainly used as a medium to distribute Islam in Kaemba since then. Once upon a time, there were only certain people of Gowa from aristocratic family who could play the game, but it had been popular and played by the communities as time goes by. Also, it had been often performed in marriage events, and cultural festivals at provincial level and at the international level considered as traditional sports. 2) The procedure of the implementation of paraga game consists of several step and preparation. The preparations are physical preparation and psychological preparation. Other than that, the paraga players should also prepare the requirement tools such as traditional uniform, traditional music instrument which will be used to accompany the show of paraga game, and bola raga that is used to do the show of paraga game. 3) Some aspects of skill movement that must be mastered by the players is Movement skills in juggling the bola raga when standing up, sitting down, and when the player does a stack formation, Movement skills when playing the bola raga on the foot or with the hand and Movement skills when doing the last formation which is forming three stack formation, and the top most player juggle the bola raga from foot to the head with a perfect execution, that is when the bola raga sit motionlessly on top of the head of the player without falling to the ground. 4) The Physical ability aspect contained in the paraga game, there are aspect of physical ability which is the skill from the player when playing the bola raga. The forms of physical ability that exists in the game are speed, skills, accuracy, and coordination.

Keywords: paraga game, traditional sports, movement skills, physical ability

1. Introduction

Indonesia is rich of cultural diversity. Beautiful strands of culture, ethnicity, tribe and religion has graced the Earth of this archipelago. Every culture, ethnicity, tribe and religion has their own way of expression and disclosure. One of those expressions reflects in the traditional sport which is alive and thriving in each area. Traditional sport is one of the cultural relics of the ancestors that have the sincere and the pattern of local tradition. 1. The definition of traditional sports according to Mahendra (1998:52), is a form of sport activities that thrive in society. The traditional sport game is a game of community that exists and entrenches in society, grows and develops and orally passed down from generation to generation. Traditional sport is cultural Nations that nearly extinct due to the time's development. This traditional sports game is almost not played

anymore by children and adults both in remote areas up in urban areas. In addition, the traditional sports game is the nation's cultural riches assets. Traditional sports should meet the two terms which are in the form of "Sport" and also "traditional" whether it is a tradition that has already flourished for several generation, as well as in the form of a meaning that has correlation with the culture of a nation in general. (A. A. Ardiwinata, dkk, 2006). Then, it should be appointed back to show its role in trying to manifest the nation's unity. Therefore, the traditional sport game needs to get priorities larger from the Central and the regions Government to take part dig, preserve and grow back so that it can be enjoyed by all society in Indonesia. A variety of developments and the preservation efforts of traditional sport game are still not ideal and faced various constraints today, it is because this traditional sport game in this modern era was already abandoned by the younger generation due to a variety of games so advanced, modern and attractive as well as being influenced by the most advanced of culture in society in the modern era. Many people prefer to the games that more sophisticated and automatic as well as digital. The children and youth generation in this country are less inclined to know the traditional sports game. However, we need to know that the traditional sports can be the source of cultural resilience faced the invasion of global culture. Traditional sport game can be used as a shield or nation identity on the stage of globalisation. A traditional sports game that comes from the game of Indonesian's society as a cultural asset of the nation needs to be preserved and developed throughout Indonesia through a skilled power activator.

Traditional sport game is one of the elements of the national culture that still alive and thriving in any areas in Indonesia. Then, remain the importance of cultural values, the role of traditional sports in the society doesn't need to doubt anymore (potential in conveying the idea that has a whole human development). Thus the traditional sport game has been able to make a sociocultural life of Indonesian nation; it is becoming so easy to understand that the traditional sports game that develops in these areas is very meaningful in the life of the Indonesian's nation. Traditional sport game also has another dimension, namely the potential to support tourism. The uniqueness of the traditional games can interest many foreign tourists to visit Indonesia. Traditional sport game also has the impact on economic parts, especially for society in those areas where the traditional games sport alive. In addition, traditional sport games also have a positive impact for the realisation of a healthy society, fit and sleek movement. Due to it has a variety of activities and physical movement that supports health. The traditional sport game as the wealth cultural nation assets be a solid and strong foundation in the development of "nation and character" to strengthen the unity of the nation.

One of traditional sport games will be chosen and researched by the author is a traditional sports game that origin from South Sulawesi "Paraga". Paraga is a traditional game which is played by Bugis society at Makassar, South Sulawesi. The Bugis society calls it "Ma'raga" to describe Sepak Raga traditional game that hit using the feet. People of Makassar call it a'raga. This game has high value and art that is combining the art of pencak silat and agility. In the countryside of South Sulawesi, this game still holds out till today Mattulada, (1979). According Mangemba, (1959) *"The strong of Paraga game in Bugis Makassar society in South Sulawesi is also caused by philosophical meaning that was taught by the ancestors to their generations, the lesson that had been taught include some aspects of the game which are soaring kick (massempeq aratiga) means that as a vigilance that must be owned by the Empire and society against all possibility of danger from the enemy, and kicks a reply (massempeq mappalece) means that the conflict should be avoided within the community."*

The tradition of this Paraga game is a game, sport and art tradition from Bugis Makassar, South Sulawesi. Paraga is different from other traditional sport game, Sepak Takraw, Paraga is performed and played, but there is not scoring here, it is just for attraction to show the skill of the player. Paraga also played in the team with the total member in a team is 6 (six) player. In Paraga, the rattan ball is bounced back using not only the feet but also the head and hands. Then, in Paraga there is something different, passapu or the triangle Cap given with the layers of tapioca to be upright, very helpful for Paraga players while doing Sepak Raga with the head. The players also use their holsters as part of their costumes, to manipulate the ball in Paraga game. There are many varieties from player position to play the ball in Paraga. The position includes standing, sitting, squatting and laying down. Paraga ever played in various formations. One of the formations is the tower formation that is formed from a pile of players standing on the shoulders of other players until the shape of the tower. The Paraga ball is also different with the rattan ball that was often used in Sepak Takraw. One Paraga ball intact has three layers of woven rattan. One layer of webbing takes about 45 minutes of creation. So, it takes about two hours to weave one Paraga ball. Most players can create their own Paraga ball. So, if any part of the ball broke, they can fix it right away. After the Paraga ball was made, this requires special treatment before play. Supposedly, the balls that is used by Paraga players has the special mantras from the teacher or senior players the Paraga players for safety and the cohesiveness of the players is kept while playing the Paraga. The Paraga game is a combination of some elements such as; game, sports, and traditional Arts of Bugis, Makassar which have a value of its own beauty.

The art of this sports culture is always played with a musical accompaniment that consists of a drum, gong, puwi-puwi, and calung-calung, such as a musical

instrument made from bamboo and it is played by hit it with a piece of wood so that the players stay excited. The Paraga players move bouncing the ball while dancing follows the accompaniment percussion music that was played. In General in Makassar, in various ceremonial or the feast of society, the Paraga game is still held to support the event. The Paraga players are usually the youths who have skill and well trained. They wear traditional clothes consisting of passappu (the headscarf typical of Makassar shaped triangle), armour lid (traditional coats) and lipa sabbe (typical Makassar Holster made of silk fabric); this youth then shows their skill wearing that entire outfit. Until today, the strong of the Islamic pattern still attaches to the attractions of the Paraga game; each time doing the Paraga attractions, the players often said "Lailahailallah" with a regular tone. It is done to keep the concentration in a game with the high level of difficulty. Now the Paraga movement is able to do with the level three of formations, where the movement formed a human stage while continuing to play physical ball up to the players who are at the top has stood in its position. This movement makes now on every show made the audience anxiously and proud when watched the ability of Paraga players who combines art, physical ability and religious overtones. In General in Indonesia, there are various areas that have a culture of sport game that is worth to be eternal and was introduced to foreign countries. For example, in South Sulawesi has a traditional games sport, namely Paraga games, and in Northern Sumatra in the Nias district, there is the tradition of the jump rock (fahombo).

Bugis people, as one of the Indonesian biggest ethnics, has 41,90 % of the total population in Sulawesi Selatan (Suryadinata, 2003 in Abdullah dkk, 2009:234) Pelras, (2006:4) continuing the explanation about the people of Bugis Makassar is that each and every one of them actually have various interesting particularity. They are a rare example that exists in the archipelago. They were able to establish kingdoms totally uninfluenced by Indian, and without establishing the city as the center of their activities. Bugis Makassar Literature, whether oral or written, has remained being read and copied. The combination between oral tradition and literary writing was then produced one of the world's largest literary epics, namely La Galigo which longer than Mahabharata. Bugis culture is often associated with Makassar culture, then it is called Bugis-Makassar (Mattulada in Koentjaraningrat, 1999). The Bugis Makassar is two Ethnic tribes that are neighbouring it could even say we can't distinguish between the two tribes, but from some aspects of culture, arts and traditions of each tribe have a difference. Moreover, it is very often we hear 'Bugis' and 'Makassar' in the same time, so that there are many people think that the word 'Bugis' and 'Makassar' is a synonym. Then, even the local scientist themselves take a part in eliminating the difference of the two tribes with pronounced and write those two terms be one unity: "Bugis Makassar".

This trend is indeed based on the various similarities to their identity as the two neighbouring tribes that transcend tribe and their language. They are, perhaps, two tribes in the archipelago, which is the hierarchy system, are very rigid and cumbersome. It is black and white. The process of acculturation in all aspects of life, including the art of literature, creates a variety of cultural similarities between the two tribes. During the civilisation of those two tribes, there are several characteristics inherent in the human life. One of them is how to keep it hierarchical and modern sighted at the same time, the support for competitive and compromise, uphold the honour but also take care of solidarity. Bravery values, intelligence, adherence to religious teachings, divines in business are variable that drives a dynamic life of Bugis and Makassar society during this time. They are typically having strong characteristic and respect honour, if necessary for the sake of retaining the honour, they are willing to do acts of violence. No matter positive law threatens them. This behaviour is often hidden with the term "Siri". In the life of the Bugis and Makassar society, Siri is a very principled element within them. There is no one else that is most precious values to be defended and preserved upfront Earth other than the Siri. The Siri is their soul, self-esteem, and their dignity as human beings. They think that their life was ended and it is not useful to live longer when their proud and shy broke or broken by someone else. Regardless of the several equations and the strong relationship and put the mutual respect, it is very needed to insist that the Bugis and Makassar keep two different tribes. The Bugis society has a population of more than four million people, inhabiting most of the Mainland and the hills next to the middle and the South. While the Makassar society with a population more than two million people settled at the southern end of the peninsula, spread along the waterfront or in a mountain range. For example, in terms of language, the two parties both Bugis and Makassar cannot understand each other when they interact with each other.

South Sulawesi is a province of Indonesia in the South part of Sulawesi with the Makassar as a capital city it is located at coordinates 0° 12'-8° South latitude and 116°48'-122°36' East longitude. A wide of the area is 45,764.53 km². The province is bordered by Central Sulawesi and West Sulawesi province to the North, the Bay of Bone and the South East Sulawesi in the East, Makassar Strait in a west and the Flores Sea in the South. The area is in South Sulawesi in the Mandar and Toraja. The four tribes had different customs so that each tribe has different ways of life also in the social and cultural aspects.

Movement skill in sport is a movement task optimally in accordance with its ability. One of the things that support the implementation of traditional sport is creation the skills of movement, entertainment, pleasure, and the need for social interaction,

sport also has the potential to improve the quality of physical for the culprit, it is very important in the performance tradition of sport game, keep in mind that a mastery of skill and techniques in sports game is very necessary for the player for the sake of continuity and smoothness in the play a movement that fits properly. According to Sugiyanto (2015: 28), movement skills (Motor skills) are a quality level of mastery in doing body movement activities in which the coordination of multiple parts of the body or the whole body can function properly. Someone said to have a skilled movement when a person is able to do the movements correctly, coefficient, and effectively also it is considered correct if the implementation of the movement is in accordance with the mechanical principles in the system of body movement. Efficient movement is a movement that can generate the best result with a very insignificant energy used. On the other hand, it is effective if the execution of the movement is in accordance with the will and the purpose wanted to achieve when doing the movement. Movement skill is one of the most important things in sports, because without a good movement and perfect skill, then the person is not able to carry out the good movements in carrying out activity related to exercise. Therefore, the movement skill is needed and was very instrumental in working out. Skill is the illustration of movement skill of someone who showed the improvement of a movement. Movement skill is the change of skills acquired through a planned movement learning program, a systematic and sustainable way. The main purpose of the movement improves learning skills. People are judged as someone who has a skill if they skilled to do something specific with the good move. The term movement skills (motor skills) conceptually can be interpreted in two ways. First, the skills are seen as a task or work (tasks), and the second skill is seen as adequate for the performance skills (level of performance proficiency) that can distinguish high and low skill level. In order for the purpose of learning and skills of movement achieved well, then any person should have good movement skills elements, which include: (1) the elements of physical capabilities that include: strength, endurance, agility and a sharpness of senses, (2) the element of mental abilities.

Physical ability is the ability to change precisely the direction of bodies or body parts without interruption on the balance. Agility is the ability to change the body position fast and exact. Physical skills are a skill, ability and efforts to change the movements and body positioning properly and precisely without losing body balance in certain space. Skills are influenced by power, fairness, balances, positions of the center of gravity, skill, and coordination. According to Dangsina Moeloek (1984:8) using the term skills. Skills are an ability to change the direction of the body or part of the body precisely without resulting any disturbance on the body balance. Skills as a skill to change body position quickly and precisely. Therefore, in doing the game of Paraga, it

highly needs physical skills, in order to make a perfect paraga game. And thus, it can be concluded that without a good physical ability, we cannot play the game of paraga perfectly. Therefore, in doing the Paraga game needs Physical ability, to create the perfect Paraga game. Thus, it can be concluded that without good physical ability we can't play physical ball well. Based on the background that has been expressed above, the author wants to do a study, entitled "*Paraga Game as Traditional Sports for Bugis Makassar Tribal Communities in South Sulawesi Indonesia*".

2. Research Method

The location of this research is the studio of cultures that nurture and perpetuate the game of Paraga, in South Sulawesi. This research uses descriptive qualitative. The qualitative method is a research procedure that produces data descriptive in a form of words both written and oral from a community group behaviour observed. The subject in this study is all potential seen in the Paraga game as traditional sports for bugis makassar tribal communities in south Sulawesi study of phenomenology reviewed from movement skill. The object of the research is done in the studio of cultures that nurture and perpetuate the game of Paraga residing in South Sulawesi, as in a society that recognized as experts or sources of information about the history of the show, the society who play Paraga performances itself, and some audience who watched the performances of Paraga. A data collection technique in this research was done by three stages that are observation, interview and documentation.

3. Results and Discussion

- 1) Identify the history of the development Paraga game at the Bugis and Makassar society in South Sulawesi.

Since ancient times up to now Paraga experience some shift of functions, even among the society of South Sulawesi have already considered this game as traditional sports and is a cultural heritage that should be preserved. Historically, lontara this game is shown as a media event for the inauguration of the Kings (somba), in Gowa Kingdoms to entertain the kingdom's guests. It is said that the first sport played ball at the moment of the game was invented and performed by "To manurung" is a ball sport derived from heaven, and made from gold (raga bulaeng). As the development of this game in society of South Sulawesi, based on stories passed down through generations in Kaemba Maros society, that in Kaemba village found a Paraga village that was Ujung bulo is a village which was once visited by the King (karaeng) from the Kingdom of

Gowa, which spread Islam and introduced the traditional musical instruments like drum (ganrang) and gong, which makes the performance of Paraga was no longer shown with movements as usual, but is now accompanied by traditional instruments. Then since that time, it ensured that Paraga was made as the medium to spread Islam in Kaemba. Some experts contend that the traditional sports football is a forerunner to the birth of the sport of sepak takraw. Due to in a Malay historical records, during the reign of Sultan Mansur Shah Ibni the deceased Sultan Muzaffar Shah (1459-1468) in line with its development in the 1940 's, the pattern of this game changed by using nets and regulation numbers. This sport evolved in Asia, it was up to in the Philippines known as Sipa, and then in Burma it is known as Chinlone, and Laos Kator and in Thailand known as Takraw. In the past only certain people of a noble family of the Kingdom of Gowa can play this game, but over the time the Paraga game has been popular and played among society of South Sulawesi. Moreover it is often displayed as a custom in traditional wedding event, and contested in cultural festival either in provincial level and international level that the position as a traditional sport.

2) Identify the society point of view towards Paraga game in South Sulawesi.

Local people are very enthusiastic when watching the Paraga game, most of them pleased saw the show of attractive and unique Paraga game attractions to behold. The existence of this game in the society of South Sulawesi is already popular and well known because it is often shown in cultural festivities events and wedding events, especially in Makassar city, and Maros in Gowa Regency.

3) Identify the ways of implementing the Paraga game played by the society of South Sulawesi.

The rules for implementing Paraga game in South Sulawesi need some preparation, including the physical and mental preparation for performing well in play ball sports attractions so that looks unique and interesting. However regardless of that Paraga player should prepare equipment for staging the game like ball, custom clothing, that are, kantiung clothes, barocci pants, lipa sabbe a custom Holster from Bugis land, passapu an fastener head typical from Makassar, and several traditional instruments, such as ganrang (drums), gong, calung-calung, puwi-puwi and tawa-tawa. Then after preparing everything, then the Paraga players prepare for the show in front of the audience who will see.

4) Identify the aspects of movement skill in the Paraga game.

Some aspects of movement skills that must be mastered by the Paraga players is movement skills to played the ball in standing or sitting position, movement skill at the time in stacked position when form of formation, movement skill at the time of play the

ball with hands, and movement skill when lifting the ball up the head using feet and the ball stay at the head without falling to the ground.

5) Identifies physical ability aspect in Paraga game.

The Physical ability aspect contained in the paraga game, there are aspect of physical ability which is the skill from the player when playing the bola raga. The form of physical ability that exists in the game is speed, skills, accuracy, and coordination.

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of field data and theoretic discussion, the conclusions of this study are:

1) The history of paraga game as a traditional sport in the society of bugis makassar ethnic in Sulawesi Selatan.

The game of paraga experiencing a fast growth, from both the implementation or the change of the function. The paraga game which played by the society of bugis makassar ethnic in Sulawesi selatan is created as a media for an inauguration ceremony of a king (Somba) at the kingdom of Gowa. The society of bugis makassar ethnic believe that the first bola raga being played is bola raga which came from the sky in the shape of bola raga emas (raga bulaeng). At the reign of kingdom gowa, only select noble people that can play the show of paraga game, but by the flow of the time, paraga game now preserved among the society and made as a cultural heritage by the society of bugis makassar ethnic. The game of paraga can often be seen at the cultural ceremony, and wedding party, especially in the area of kabupaten gowa, maros, and makassar. The game nowadays often being held at the province level of Sulawesi selatan at the culture festival event by the tourism department of the Sulawesi selatan province, and it even being held in international level, which considered as a traditional sport. The game of paraga represent Sulawesi selatan province as a traditional sport, that being contested in the arena of traditional sport match, on the international level of the association for international sport for all world games (TAFISA) program, as known as the game of social Olympics, and considered as the match of the traditional sport. This traditional sport arena is being contested by 29 provinces in Indonesia and 87 nations in the world, which is being held at ancol Jakarta on the year of 2016. In the reign of the late sultan Mansur shah ibni sultan muzaffar shah (1459-1477) in 1940, the pattern of bola raga sport changed with nets and regulatory figures. This sport then evolved in asia region, such as in the Philippines known as the (Sipa), in Burma known as (Chinlone), and in Laos kator and also Thailand known as (Takraw). From this, scientists and cultural

anthropology found paraga game or traditional sepak raga is the genesis and origin of the birth of sepak takraw.

- 2) Procedure for the implementation of paraga game which played by the society of bugis makassar ethnic in Sulawesi selatan.

The procedure of the implementation of paraga game consists of several step and preparation. The preparations are physical preparation and psychological preparation. Other than that, the paraga players should also prepare the requirement tools such as traditional uniform, traditional music instrument which will be used to accompany the show of paraga game, and bola raga that is used to do the show of paraga game. These are the procedures of paraga game as follows:

- a. First, the players do a salute to the spectator of the game.
- b. Then the players pray together for the safety when playing the game.
- c. A referee enters the field and stand in the middle, followed by the players that make a circle. The game begins by the referee holding the bola raga and then throwing it up away, the player who got the raga play first, and they are the one who will initiate the game.
- d. The last when the players doing a formation of Menara tiga dua satu which requires a solid teammate by forming a stack of 3 rows and the most upper player play the ball by doing a juggle to the bola raga with a considerable amount of concentrations and skills, until at the point where the show become attractive and the last thing to do for the player is by playing the ball on their head and the ball stopped moving, and the bola raga perfectly motionless on top of the player's head. This attraction is a maneuver action which has the highest rank if the player could execute it perfectly when doing the performance.

- 3) Aspect of movement skills in the game of paraga.

There are some forms of Movement skills in the paraga game, they are as follows:

- a. Movement skills in juggling the bola raga when standing up, sitting down, and when the player does a stack formation.
- b. Movement skills when playing the bola raga on the foot or with the hand.
- c. Movement skills when doing the last formation which is forming three stack formation, and the top most player juggle the bola raga from foot to the head with a perfect execution, that is when the bola raga sit motionlessly on top of the head of the player without falling to the ground.
- 4) Aspect of physical ability which exists in the paraga game.

In the paraga game, there are aspect of physical ability which is the skill from the player when playing the bola raga. The form of physical ability that exists in the game are speed, skills, accuracy, and coordination.

- a. Physical ability in the forms of skills, speed, and accuracy that can be seen when the player does a juggling on bola raga whilst standing, sitting, and when doing the formation. And then it can also be seen when the player is playing the ball with their foot and when they juggle the ball whilst passing it to the teammate.
- b. Physical ability in the forms of skills, accuracy, speed and coordination when the player is playing bola raga and then do a maneuver so the ball placed in the head by using foot or hand, at the point where the bola raga stop moving on top of the player's head. And thus, it can be concluded that without a good physical ability from the players, they will not be able to play the bola raga perfectly and attractively.

5. Suggestion

Based on the conclusions that have been described above, then the suggestion from writers are:

1. Department of youth and sports is expected to be a little more notice and consider to develop and always make the event or activity, contested the traditional sport game especially *Paraga* game in South Sulawesi.
2. The Department of culture and tourism of South Sulawesi is expected to pay attention, manage, and develop the traditional sports especially *Paraga* in South Sulawesi.
3. The Government of the province of South Sulawesi is expected to give a contribution in the form of funds to renovate the new *Paraga* Studios in South Sulawesi and help several studios to educate the future generation of *Paraga* player.
4. The *Paraga* game is made as icons or ways by the local government in South Sulawesi province that has a wealth of culture and customs to attract foreign tourists to pay a visit to South Sulawesi.
5. An appeal to the community of South Sulawesi to always keep the *Paraga* game, because this game is not cultural relics items should be preserved so that the game continues to exist and is not lost over time.

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